

Methodical instructions on the organization of physical education in Uzbekistan via national traditions

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Abstract:

The article discusses the role of physical education in the education system of Uzbekistan. The views on methodological instruction in the use of national traditions in the organization of physical education in higher education are based on scientific evidence.

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Introduction

In the socio-cultural potential of Uzbekistan, physical culture and sports have their own content, shape, purpose and meaning. Activities of physical culture and sports professionals to carry out such large-scale events as inculcating them into the culture of daily living, nurturing the physical well-being of young people, attracting talented young people to the sport, enhancing their fame through the sport. deserves attention (Crook, 1996; Ergasheva, Vasieva, & Murtazova, 2019; Ibragimovna, 2019; Mukhtarov, Fox, Mukhamedova, & Wegerich, 2015).

One of the problems of the present is training of specialists of physical culture and sport, deepening of their knowledge and constant increase of practical skills, creativity and initiative.

The basics of specialization in theoretical disciplines are "Theory and Methods of Physical Culture", "History and Management of Physical Education", "Methods of Teaching Sport and Active Games" at almost all levels of Physical Education faculties. , methodology and ways of its implementation. Theoretical knowledge related to the organization of different levels of production of the population, physical education, sports, travel and national games in educational institutions the basic concepts are not expressed in the least(BOBUR et al., 2015; Buhalis & O'Connor, 2005; Robel, 2004).

It should be admitted that in the textbook by K. Yarashev "Physical Culture and Sport Management" (2001), the above-mentioned problems are clearly explained. There is also a need to organize the educational process on the organization of mass physical culture, tourism and national games at the faculties of physical culture. However, work in this area has not been done sufficiently. In all educational institutions and universities of the republic (TSPU, SamSU, KokandPMI, FarSU, NamSU, etc.) in the curriculum of the Faculty of Physical Culture on the basis of sections "Selected subjects", "Special courses". hours, which provide theoretical concepts and practical skills. It explains some of the concepts of national values, spiritual and educational culture. The initiator of these activities was Associate Professor XA Meliev, the author of this thesis. Involvement of senior students in Navruz, Independence Day, Pentecost, Vocational Days (teachers, health workers, etc.) and equip them with practical and organizational skills in this field. Experience of creative work (Association Of Business Schools, 2015; Kalpakjian & Schmid, 2014; News & 2017, n.d.).

They argue that the faculty is teaching a lot of theoretical subjects for students, but there is little indication that national and traditional events should be taught more and that students should be involved in practical activities. These considerations may

be more or less logical. However, future physical education teachers and coaches should be encouraged to learn national values and traditions separately.

According to the aforementioned university professors and some of the leading experts in other areas, spirituality and enlightenment work with teachers on national independence, pedagogy, cultural studies and related subjects. There is no direct link between the teachers of the education faculties regarding these problems. They are only teaching the subject areas of their subject matter. In our opinion, in all areas of study and education, there should be activities, creativity and initiative that educate professionals to nurture the spiritual and physical development of future professionals. Only then can future professionals be highly educated, proud of their national values, and be fully aware of their responsibilities and responsibilities towards the people, their homeland (Affairs & 2005, n.d.; Lv, Guo, & Chen, 2018; Macleod & By, 2007).

The practical management of such requirements should be related to the working conditions of the labor collectives, various institutions, residential areas, places of rest and leisure, social work conditions. That is, they need to set up staff based on the needs and needs of coaches, organizers of mass health, physical education and sporting activities, or to order the required sports organizations or undergraduate and secondary education institutions. will need to be adjusted. If these activities are

followed, it will be possible to increase the number of organizers in specific areas, to spread national traditions and to use them in their activities.

The state educational standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2015) and qualification requirements are aimed at ensuring the continuity of physical education in educational institutions, involvement of students and students in mass sports activities. On this basis, the Physical Education Program (2014) for higher education and academic lyceums, vocational colleges and colleges has been developed and is being implemented. On March 1, 2000 special tests “Alpomish” and “Barchinoy” were introduced. Their content, form and purpose are the main options for the development of student and youth physical education and the ability to work and defend.

The goals and objectives of mass reforms in the sphere of culture, medicine, education and sports, their content fully meet the requirements of the time, the education of young people in the profession. It requires that you have all the qualities that are associated with your devotion to your homeland and your beliefs. The point is that the above-mentioned Physical Education programs provide a comprehensive overview of how to use national values in physical education classes, especially the use of national traditions in physical education, sports, travel and national games. no. This has a negative impact on students' perceptions of national traditions and their understanding of the importance of physical education. Most teachers do not have to

leave the program; creative approach and practical initiatives are rare. These negative traits are particularly evident in student learning (pedagogical and organizational).

As you know, the physical education process has its own peculiarities. When analyzing the curriculum for the Physical Culture curriculum, there are two main areas:

1. Students are trained in selected sports in a form, content and method that is common to all faculties in the Republic and at their own DJTI.

2. There are courses in the specialties of the faculty and the specialties they are interested in. These processes have a positive effect on students to acquire a certain degree of special understanding and knowledge. However, this situation is well established in all universities and their quality is not high. There are also some objective and subjective reasons for this:

- educational manuals and recommendations on social and educational features of national traditions and customs are not developed;
- The knowledge of traditions is much weaker for teachers working to develop theoretical knowledge and practical skills in sports;
- In the abstracts, courses and graduation (diploma) issues of spiritual and physical maturity are not covered in detail;

- The content and significance of mass cultural events held in the I-II stages of physical culture education in housekeeping, independent work and sports facilities.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Development of Physical Education and Mass Sports" dated June 3, 2017, the selection of talented children, their experimentation and their mobilization to sports schools is attached. In these organizational, practical and educational conditions, national performances and mass demonstrations can play an important role (Ergasheva et al., 2019; Tao, Kaplan, & Omenetto, 2012). For this reason, students of all levels of the Physical Culture Faculty are expected to share with each other the skills of children's sports and national traditions; it is necessary to teach organizational methods of proportionality. Such social and educational activities and activities should be taught in all theoretical and practical (sports) lessons and exercises.

Training courses and sport activities in the curriculum (gymnastics, athletics, movement games, wrestling, specialization, etc.) and special training courses for Alpomish and Barchinoy The tests continued to symbolize the lives of our ancestors, reminiscent of traditional customs and traditions, expressed in the context of national values in teaching test-and-test requirements. However, it is important to provide students with information about the Alpomish epic and other artifacts, historical, cultural and archaeological sources.

As in every field, it is one of the main activities to provide sufficient theoretical knowledge and practical skills to train physical education teachers. According to the curriculum of the Physical Culture faculties, the practice (pedagogical and organizational training) is planned for 18 weeks (6-8 semesters). The first half of Phase III focuses on physical education and extracurricular activities and on-site support for teachers. At the beginning of the second half of the fourth year, students will be conducting exemplary physical education classes, analyzing their lessons, conducting classes in sports, management of mass sports, and refereeing.

The theoretical analysis of the results of pedagogical observations, formal interviews with experienced teachers, undergraduate students, and interviews led to the following comments:

- responsible teachers of the Department of Theory and Methods of Physical Education, Specialty in Sports and Department of Pedagogy and Psychology;

- instructors (methodologists) in their preparation of the morning practice for the practice, consistently study and monitor their interest, theoretical concepts and practical activities;

- In the special conferences (conferences) held to conduct practical training, faculty leaders and department heads present students with their main activities;

- teachers of physical culture, staff of city (district) sports committees, the Youth Association, participating in the conference (on an invitation) exchange experience;
- the responsibility of school administrators to provide practical assistance and practical assistance in schools for conducting practice activities;
in the mornings, they set a good example in their work and diligent study of their tasks.

In general, the interaction between the school and the faculty in the process of preparing and conducting the internship is significant. However, there are serious shortcomings, shortcomings, and shortcomings in the study and application of national traditions in education, especially in professional practice. These are:

1. Lack of theoretical knowledge of the students to carry out the internship at a high level. Because, for one reason or another, practical experience in training, organizing competitions, attracting and engaging students.

2. Most students are good at physical education, physical culture, and organizational techniques in sports

It shows that they are not trained and not fully aware of sports news.

3. Lack of control over the methodology of the faculty and constant analysis of students' activities causes them to neglect their duties.

4. There is a shortage of physical education teachers to provide practical assistance to their students.

5. Students have low levels of evidence for creativity, coursework, or graduation.

6. Ensuring students' active participation in mass sports and competitions is not well organized.

7. The use of traditions in the work of the School Spirituality and Enlightenment, the Youth Social Movement Kamolot, the Council of Physical Education "Yoshlik", class leaders and other formal elementary organizations

In short, there are very few conversations and practical activities about the study of national values in the practice, the use of national traditions in the education process, and their social and educational features.

Conclusion

To summarize, the literature on physical culture and sports shows that the content of national traditions is not fully reflected in the events held.

In the context of scientific research carried out in the Republic, little attention is paid to the national features of physical education, sports, travel and national games, as well as their social and educational processes. One of the main reasons for this is that physical education teachers are only engaged in training, and coaches in sports are only engaged in coaching.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that the emphasis on improving the quality of education in the National Program for Personnel Training has made the need to organize the process of physical education through national traditions.

This necessity dictated the organization of physical education through the national traditions. However, the solution of this problem requires that its entire system be implemented in accordance with the requirements of scientific organization and reform of the education system. In general, reforming the content of physical education and teaching is one of the pressing problems of the day.

It is known that the process of physical education reform has its own peculiarities. Its main areas are the improvement of theoretical knowledge and practical aspects, the acquisition of students' knowledge, regular improvement of professional skills, the formation of national ideas and ideologies in their minds, the organization of the educational process. The harmonious use of national traditions in the production of fruits and vegetables will bring effective results.

However, in practice programs, manuals and textbooks do not fully solve the problem. Therefore, a new approach to the organization of physical education, search for effective forms and methods is one of the important tasks of the day.

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